

Nomenclatural novelties in Myrtaceae

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Abstract: New names *Myrcianthes aemula* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *Syzygium amboinense* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar and *S. axillare* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar are proposed for the illegitimate names *Eugenia aemula* Diels, *E. amboinensis* Greves and *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton respectively. To fix the identity and to avoid the misapplication of names, lectotypes are designated for *E. aemula* Diels, *E. amboinensis* Greves and *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton.

Keywords: Ecuador, Endemic, *Eugenia aemula*, *Eugenia amboinensis*, *Eugenia axillaris*, Indonesia, Lectotype

Introduction

The New World genus *Myrcianthes* O.Berg is represented by 40 species (POWO, 2024). In Republic of Ecuador, the genus is represented by 12 species, namely *M. aemula* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *M. alaternifolia* (Benth.) Grifo ex B.Holst & M.L.Kawas., *M. discolor* (Kunth) McVaugh, *M. fimbriata* (Kunth) McVaugh, *M. fragrans* (Sw.) McVaugh, *M. hallii* (O.Berg) McVaugh, *M. lindleyana* (Kunth) McVaugh, *M. myrsinoides* (Kunth) Grifo, *M. orthostemon* (O.Berg) Grifo, *M. prodigiosa* McVaugh, *M. rhopaloides* (Kunth) McVaugh and *M. rubra* B.Holst & M.L.Kawas. *M. aemula* and *M. rubra* is endemic (POWO, 2024). In current circumscription, *Eugenia aemula* Diels needs to be transferred to the genus *Myrcianthes*, but the name *Eugenia aemula* Diels is illegitimate and later homonym of *E. aemula* (Blume) Koord. & Valeton. Therefore, a new name *Myrcianthes aemula* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar is proposed here for the illegitimate name *Eugenia aemula* Diels. In addition, to fix the identity and to avoid misapplication of the name *E. aemula* Diels, the lectotype is designated here.

The Old-World genus *Syzygium* Gaertn. consists of about 1237 species (POWO, 2024). In

Republic of Indonesia, the genus is represented by 423 species, of which 27 are endemic, viz. *S. abatakum* Widodo, *S. acutatum* (Miq.) Amshoff, *S. aemulum* (Blume) Amshoff, *S. amboinense* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *S. ampliflorum* (Koord. & Valeton) Amshoff, *S. angustovatum* Widodo & Chikmaw., *S. axillare* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *S. blumei* (Steud.) Merr. & L.M.Perry, *S. comosum* Widodo, *S. discophorum* (Koord. & Valeton) Amshoff, *S. fraternum* Miq., *S. glomeruliferum* Amshoff, *S. horsfieldii* (Miq.) Widodo, *S. inopinatum* Amshoff, *S. ketambense* Widodo, *S. klampok* (Miq.) Amshoff, *S. longipetiolatum* Widodo, *S. microcymum* (Koord. & Valeton) Amshoff, *S. minimum* (Blume) Airy Shaw, *S. nusatenggaraense* Sunarti & Y.W.Low, *S. pachyrrachis* Amshoff, *S. splendens* (Blume) Merr. & L.M.Perry, *S. subcapitulatum* Miq., *S. teretiflorum* (Koord. & Valeton) Amshoff, *S. triplinervium* Teijsm. & Binn., *S. vrieseanum* (Miq.) Amshoff and *S. winckelii* Amshoff (POWO, 2024). In current circumscription, the two names *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves and *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton needs to be transferred to the genus *Syzygium*. However, the names *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves and *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton are illegitimate and later homonyms of *E. amboinensis* Nois. ex Link and *E. axillaris* (Sw.) Willd. respectively. Therefore, two new names *Syzygium amboinense* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar and *S. axillare* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar are proposed here for the two illegitimate names *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves and *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton respectively. Lectotypes are designated here for *E. amboinensis* Greves and *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton to fix the identity and to avoid the misapplication of names. We followed the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 in Turland et al. (2018).

Nomenclature

Myrcianthes aemula R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Eugenia aemula* Diels, Beibl. Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 91: 47. 1907, *nom. illeg., non* (Blume) Koord. & Valeton, Meded. Lands Plantentuin 40: 76. 1900.

Lectotype (designated here): Ecuador, Forests of the Quito province, *s.d.*, A. Sodiro *s.n.* (P05156450!, Figure 1).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Ecuador.

Notes: While describing *Eugenia aemula*, Diels (1907) cited the type information as “Ecuador: in silvis subandinis provinciae Quito, flor. m. Oct. 1882 (S. n. 458 — Herb. Berol.!)”. Diels’s types are known to be held at B (Stafleu & Mennega, 1998). Presently, no holotype or other original material is extant for the name *E. aemula* Diels at B. One duplicate of the holotype is traced at P (P05156450) and is designated here as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

Syzygium amboinense R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves, J. Bot. 62(Suppl.): 36. 1924, *nom. illeg., non* Nois. ex Link, Enum. Hort. Berol. Alt. 2: 28. 1822.

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Eugenia aemula* Diels (P05156450, © Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris)

Figure 2: Lectotype of *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves (BM000944219, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 3: Isolectotype of *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves (WU0045762, © Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, Universität Wien)

Figure 4: Lectotype of *Eugenia axillaris* Koord. & Valeton (A00069458, © Herbarium of the Arnold Arboretum, Harvard University)

Figure 5: *Eugenia axillaris* Koord. & Valeton (Atlas Baumart. Java 3: t. 448. 1914)

Lectotype (designated here): Indonesia, Maluku Province, Amboina (Ambon Island), 1882, H.O. Forbes 3267 (BM000944219!, Figure 2); isolectotype WU0045762! (Figure 3).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Indonesia (Maluku Province).

Notes: Two original specimens for the name *Eugenia amboinensis* Greves were traced (BM000944219 and WU0045762). The best one, BM000944219, is designated here as the lectotype.

Syzygium axillare R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Eugenia axillaris* Koord. & Valeton, Bull. Inst. Bot. Buitenzorg 2: 6. 1899; Bijdr. Boomsort. Java 6: 60. 1900; Atlas Baumart. Java 3: t. 448. 1914, *nom. illeg., non* (Sw.) Willd., Sp. Pl., ed. 4. 2: 960. 1799 et Vell., Fl. Flumin. 209. 1829 et G.Don, Gen. Hist. 2: 866. 1832.

Lectotype (designated here): Indonesia, Java, *s.d.*, S.H. Koorders 5528B (A00069458!, Figure 4).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Indonesia (Java).

Notes: At present, only one original specimen (A00069458) is extant for the name *Eugenia axillaris* Koord. & Valeton, which is designated here as the lectotype. Backer (1945) treated *E. axillaris* Koord. & Valeton under *Syzygium pycnanthum* Merr. & L.M.Perry, but it differs in leaf and flower characters as mentioned by Koorders & Valeton (1900). The type specimen and illustration (Figure 5) given by Koorders & Valeton (1914) for *Eugenia axillaris* Koord. & Valeton is very different from *Syzygium pycnanthum* Merr. & L.M.Perry.

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